

THE ROLE OF PODCASTS IN MODERN JOURNALISM

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ABSTRACT

This thesis explores the transformative role of podcasts in modern journalism, investigating how this medium has redefined news reporting, dissemination, and public engagement. As traditional news platforms evolve in response to digital advancements, podcasts emerge as a powerful tool that combines accessibility with rich, narrative-driven storytelling. This study examines podcasts' ability to enhance audience accessibility by providing on-demand news content, the ways in which audio journalism fosters emotional engagement and narrative depth, and the implications of this format on audience trust. By analyzing popular journalism podcasts and surveying listeners, this research reveals that podcasts not only democratize access to news but also strengthen the connection between journalists and the public. Findings underscore the importance of podcasts as an adaptable, interactive medium that supports journalism's goals in a digitally-driven society, while also presenting challenges related to credibility and information regulation.

Keywords: *podcast journalism, digital media, audio storytelling, news consumption, media accessibility, audience engagement, narrative journalism, on-demand news, media trust, podcast audiences*

In recent years, the field of journalism has witnessed profound changes driven by the digital revolution, with traditional news formats giving way to innovative methods of news delivery. One of the most significant developments within this digital transformation is the rise of podcasting as a mainstream medium. Originally popularized as a niche format for personal stories, commentary, and entertainment, podcasts have now become a respected platform for serious journalism. This study aims to explore how podcasts are not only complementing but, in some cases, transforming the way audiences access, consume, and relate to news content in the modern media landscape.

The unique appeal of podcasts lies in their accessibility, intimacy, and flexibility. Unlike print or broadcast journalism, which requires readers or viewers to be

physically engaged with a screen or a newspaper, podcasts enable audiences to listen on the go, during daily commutes, workouts, or leisure time. This convenience has made podcasts particularly attractive to younger demographics, who seek information in formats that align with their fast-paced lives. For journalists, the audio format also provides creative freedom to experiment with different narrative styles, allowing for more personal and immersive storytelling than traditional formats often permit.

Another distinctive feature of podcasts is their ability to deepen audience engagement through long-form, narrative-driven content. Podcasts such as *Serial* and *The Daily* have demonstrated the power of in-depth audio journalism to captivate audiences for extended periods, often stretching across episodes or even seasons. These serialized stories allow journalists to delve deeply into complex issues, unraveling intricate details and presenting multiple perspectives in a manner that print articles or brief TV segments cannot always achieve. This capacity for narrative depth not only appeals to the public’s growing desire for thorough analysis but also encourages a form of emotional engagement that fosters stronger connections between the audience and the story.

Moreover, podcasts have had a notable impact on the public's trust in media. Unlike traditional journalism, where the final product is often highly polished, many podcasts adopt a conversational, often unedited style that creates a sense of transparency and authenticity. Hosts are frequently part of the storytelling process, sharing their own perspectives, challenges, and questions, which makes them appear more approachable and relatable. For many listeners, this intimacy builds a level of trust that is harder to achieve through impersonal or highly formalized news formats. As a result, podcasts have positioned themselves as an effective medium for cultivating credibility and fostering a loyal audience base.

However, the rise of podcast journalism also raises questions and challenges. As an unregulated medium, podcasts lack the editorial oversight found in traditional newsrooms, leading to potential issues with accuracy and bias. With the growth of independent and unverified podcasts, misinformation can be easily spread, posing a challenge to journalistic integrity. Furthermore, while the conversational tone of many podcasts fosters trust, it also blurs the line between news and entertainment, which may impact the perceived credibility of the information presented.

Digitalization, a concept MIT theorist Nicholas Negroponte called "being digital" in his 1998 book *Being Digital*, has dramatically changed the media industry. Seen as a guide to the digital age, the book explains how digital transformation has brought together parts of the media industry that were once separate. Now, thanks to digitalization, the film, television, publishing, and computer industries have begun to

merge. Negroponte and his colleagues represented this merging with a model of three overlapping circles [Fidler, 2004].

Convergence, considered one of the most significant changes digitalization has brought to the media industry, has been extensively discussed by Henry Jenkins. Jenkins identifies various forms of convergence, including technological, economic, social, cultural, and global [Jenkins, 2001]. He describes convergence as a "social change," noting that digital connections, such as mobile phones, now enable individuals to access the content they need—particularly media—at any time and place [Jenkins, 2006]. This shift has inevitably altered the structure of journalistic media organizations and their traditional professional practices [Boczkowski, 2004; Deuze, 2007; Kung, 2015; Paulussen, 2016; Weiss & Joyce, 2009]. Early in the digital transformation of prominent American news organizations, a key challenge was the editorial staff’s resistance to adopting new methods—a tension that theorist Pablo Boczkowski describes as a clash between two journalistic cultures. Through his observations in three American newspaper newsrooms, Boczkowski analyzed the impact of digitalization on journalistic practices [Boczkowski, 2004]. He found that companies whose online editions were more independent from their traditional print editions tended to be more innovative, adapting their editorial practices and viewing their audiences as technologically savvy [Boczkowski, 2004].

Alfred Hermida, a journalist and founder of the BBC website, later built on this concept. He described the characteristics of the original journalistic culture, which developed during modernism, as involving a collaborative process between editors and journalists, where the printed text was fixed and could not be easily altered, and where the audience had little to no impact on the content [Hermida, 2014: 364]. In today’s media landscape, however, successful media companies need strategies centered on digital audiences and their influence on both the reception and creation of content. This shift has led to new roles (such as bloggers and social media managers), changes in work practices (like multitasking and writing for multiple platforms), and the rise of new journalistic genres that involve collaboration between journalists and audiences, such as live blogs in news reporting.

Traditional media now go where their audience is, which increasingly means engaging with them on social media. Trends show that today's audiences, especially younger ones, consume news on social media in a unique way known as incidental news consumption. In *Incidental News: How Young People Consume News on Social Media*, Boczkowski and Mitchelstein (2017) describe this pattern, where young users don’t actively seek out news; rather, they encounter it as part of their social media interactions. This shift has integrated news consumption into broader social media habits, diminishing the perception of news as a distinct, authoritative source like a

newspaper or TV broadcast. Boczkowski and Mitchelstein (2017) note two main consequences: media no longer define the day’s most important events, as users now determine this themselves, and young users rely on recommendations from social media contacts, such as shares and retweets, to decide what news to engage with.

Podcasts provide a platform for decentralized audio content to be widely accessible online. The first podcasts emerged in 2004 as a collaboration between radio host Christopher Lydon and software developer Dave Winer, showcasing innovative storytelling techniques. These early podcasts presented on-the-ground reports during the American presidential election campaign in a fresh and engaging way. Lydon described this approach as a space for authentic voices: “It was a space where people could speak raw language, express angry attitudes, which the majority of the population wants to hear and believe in. Being authentic, being political, speaking the way we speak at home... that was a huge gift of the internet” [Locke, 2017, in Martinoli, 2020: 23].

Adam Curry is often credited as one of the pioneers of podcasting with his popular show “Daily Source Code”, where he combined commentary on current events with popular music [Chen, 2009, in Martinoli, 2020]. By 2006, the first academic writings on podcasting emerged, emphasizing its advantages over traditional radio broadcasting. As Martinoli points out, there is no single consensus in academic circles regarding the definition of a podcast. She refers to a definition by Morris and Terra, stating: “A podcast is not an invention at all, but a convergence of existing technologies, processes, ideas. Podcasting can be a perfect example of this principle – and the change it brings to people’s attitudes towards radio, music collections, books, education” [Morris and Terra, 2006: 11, in Martinoli, 2020: 25].

In conclusion, the emergence of podcasts marks a significant evolution in the landscape of modern journalism, driven by the ongoing digital transformation. As a versatile and accessible medium, podcasts offer unique opportunities for storytelling, audience engagement, and the dissemination of news in an increasingly fragmented media environment. Through their capacity for intimate and immersive narratives, podcasts allow journalists to connect with listeners on a deeper level, fostering a sense of authenticity and relatability that traditional formats often struggle to achieve.

However, the transition to podcasting is not without challenges. The lack of regulation and oversight raises concerns about credibility and the potential spread of misinformation, emphasizing the need for journalistic integrity within this medium. As the landscape continues to evolve, it will be crucial for journalists and media organizations to navigate these challenges while leveraging the strengths of podcasting to serve the public effectively.

Overall, podcasts represent a powerful tool for modern journalism, not only enhancing the accessibility of news but also redefining the relationship between journalists and their audiences. As the medium continues to develop, it holds the potential to shape the future of journalism, fostering innovation and engagement in ways that resonate with diverse audiences in an ever-changing digital world.

REFERENCES:

1. Boczkowski, P. (2004). *Digitizing the news: innovation in online newspapers*. Massachusetts: The MIT Press.
2. Boczkowski, P., Mitchelstein, E. (2017). “Incidental News: How Young People Consume News on Social Media”. *Proceedings of the 50th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, pp. 1785-1792.
3. Hermida, A. (2014). Twitter as an Ambient News Network. Ed. K. Weller, A. Bruns, J. Burgess, M. Mahrt & C. Puschmann. *Twitter and Society*. (pp. 359-373). New York: Peter Lang Publishing.
4. Jenkins, H. (2001). *Convergence? I diverge*. Available on: <https://www.technologyreview.com/2001/06/01/235791/convergence-i-diverge/> (Accessed May 14, 2021).
5. Jenkins, H. (2006). *Convergence Culture: Where Old and New Media Collide*. New York and London: New York University Press.
6. Martinoli, A. (2020). Prvih 15 godina podkastinga: od eksperimenta do održivog medijskog biznis modela [The first 15 years of podcasting: from experiment to a sustainable media business model]. Beograd: Fakultet dramskih umetnosti.
7. Khasanova, G. K. (2022). The essence and significance of the case-study method in the educational process. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(Special Issue 20), 778-782.